

Legal Document Classification and Summarization Using Multinomial Naive Bayes Classifier and TextRank

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Abstract-Lawyers and the court system face significant challenges in management and classifying legal documents. The sheer volume of legal documents, such as Contracts, Agreements, Deeds, HR documents, Tax forms, Valuations etc. makes it difficult to quickly organise and retrieve relevant information. This research study provides a machine learning-based approach for automating the classification of legal documents, with the goal of overcoming the difficulties that lawyers encounter when dealing with enormous amounts of documents. The suggested method employs the Multinomial Naive Bayes classifier, which has been trained on labelled PDF files, as well as the Count Vectorizer to convert keywords retrieved from PDFs into numerical features for input to the classifier. The trained model is saved in a pickle file for future use in predicting the category of fresh PDFs. Furthermore, the Text Rank algorithm is used to generate a summary of the PDF content, which improves the efficiency and effectiveness of the document management process even further.

Keywords- Document Classification, Document Summarization, Machine Learning, Python, Multinomial Naïve Bayes classifier.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the field of law, the needs for handling and organising legal papers have expanded substantially in recent years. Year after year, persons in the legal sector must deal with a tremendous volume of legal documents and data. Legal document management and classification are key challenges for the court system and attorneys. The massive volume of legal papers, which includes contracts, agreements, deeds, HR records, tax forms, valuations, and other documents, makes it difficult to swiftly organise and retrieve crucial information. To address these issues, this seminar paper provides a machine learning-based strategy for automating legal document classification, with the goal of overcoming the problems that attorneys have when dealing with huge volumes of data.

In this work, we trained a model on a set of labelled PDF files using the Multinomial Naive Bayes classifier, a common machine learning approach. The extracted

keywords from the PDF files were converted into numerical features that could be fed into the classifier using the CountVectorizer. The trained model was stored to a pickle file for use in predicting the category of new PDFs in the future. In addition, we employed the TextRank algorithm to create a summary of the PDF content, which further increases the efficiency and efficacy of the document management process.

Compared to typical document management approaches, our system offers significant advantages. For example, it can swiftly and accurately classify documents related to law, saving attorneys time and effort in manually classifying the documents. Second, our technique is capable of handling massive amounts of data, making it appropriate for organisations that must process significant amounts of legal documents. Finally, the TextRank algorithm gives a brief summary of the PDF text, allowing attorneys to easily extract key information.

Challenges:

- i) Data quality: The accuracy of document categorization models is strongly dependent on the quality of data extracted from the document. Missing or partial data might also have an impact on document categorization and prediction.
- ii) Limited training data: The amount and quality of training data used to train a machine learning model heavily influence its performance. In some circumstances, there may be limited labelled data available for training the model, which might influence the classification's accuracy and efficacy.
- iii) Document Variability: The structure, content, and format of legal documents can vary significantly. This variety might make it difficult to extract key characteristics and build a robust model capable of reliably classifying documents of various sorts.

iv) Multilingual documents: Legal documents can be written in multiple languages, complicating the categorization procedure even further.

v) Computational complexity: The suggested technique consists of many processes, including data extraction, feature engineering, model training, and prediction. These stages can be computationally costly, particularly when working with big amounts of data.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mariana Y. Noguti, Eduardo Vellasques, and Luiz S. Oliveira et.al in [1] Address the issue of inconsistent information in legal petitions received by the Public Prosecutor's Office of the State of Paraná in Brazil, which leads to improper classification and lengthy processing times. The authors suggest using Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques for textual categorization and comparing various approaches to word representation to automatically forecast the petitions' field of law. The research compares the efficacy of various word embedding and classification models, such as linear models, boosted trees, and neural networks. The authors discover that a combination of Word2Vec trained on a domain-specific corpus and a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) architecture, notably LSTM, gives the best results in the classification of eighteen categories (legal domains), with an accuracy of 90% and an F1-Score of 85%.

For future research, the work supplies a fresh collection of word embedding's pre-trained on Brazilian Portuguese legal documents. The authors emphasise the potential of text categorization to improve public service efficiency and propose future research objectives in this field. The research provides useful insights into the use of NLP approaches to legal documents as well as the difficulties associated with automating the categorization process of court petitions. The authors' contributions to the subject of legal document categorization offer a prospective route for increasing the efficiency of the Brazilian Public Prosecutor's Office.

Shaz Furniturewala, Racchit Jain, Vijay Kumari, and Yashvardhan Sharma et.al in [2] This study describes a method for categorising legal papers for relevance and extractive summary. For their tests, the authors use the "Artificial Intelligence for Legal Assistance" (AILA) dataset supplied by the Forum of Information Retrieval Evaluation (FIRE) 2021. The study covers the domain-specific linguistic structure of legal case papers, as well as the necessity for an automated summary approach to decrease the cost and time necessary for manual summation. The authors focus on extractive summary, which is the process of selecting the most important lines from a document and building a summary from them. In this assignment, the study also underlines the importance of relevance categorization, which requires evaluating which sentences are most relevant to the case. The authors use a combination of BERT and joint text features to accomplish relevance classification,

which came in first place in AILA task 2a with an accuracy of 0.64, recall of 0.58, and F1 score of 0.59. Overall, the work provides a novel way to relevance classification and extraction summary of legal texts by utilising cutting-edge methodologies such as BERT and joint text characteristics. The experiments' findings indicate that the approach is effective and has the potential to automate the summarization of legal documents

Christian J. Mahoney, Peter Gronvall, and others in [3]. In this study, the authors provide a paradigm for explainable text categorization in legal document review, which they have applied in their legal analytics software. Their methodology employs a supervised machine learning algorithm to categorise documents into attorney-defined categories, with a particular emphasis on detecting relevant materials. Unlike previous predictive coding systems, however, their framework includes reasons for each categorization choice, making the process visible and interpretable for attorneys. The authors provide the findings of an experiment that employed data from a real-world court case to examine documents using their methodology. They discovered that their framework boosted the efficiency and quality of document review while also increasing attorneys' trust in the outcomes of the supervised learning job. It was able to accurately identify responsive materials and offer comprehensive justifications for each categorization choice. This study emphasises the significance of establishing explainable AI systems in the legal realm in order to foster trust in the technology.

Shuo Jiang, Jie Hu, Christopher L. Magee, et.al in [4]. This paper discusses the use of TechDoc, a revolutionary multimodal deep learning architecture for document categorization that makes use of natural language text, descriptive photos, and document relationships. It classifies technical papers using a mix of convolutional neural networks (CNN), recurrent neural networks (RNN), and graph neural networks (GNN) based on the hierarchical International Patent Classification system. The authors trained the TechDoc model using a large multimodal technical document corpus and compared its classification accuracy to other state-of-the-art benchmarks. The results show that TechDoc outperforms unimodal techniques and other benchmarks, attaining higher classification accuracy. The article finds that TechDoc's capacity to harness multimodal information for document classification has the potential to minimise the time and expense involved with organising technical papers while also ensuring correct document categorization..

Bc. Jiří Mauritz [5]. The creation of automated tools to help lawyers, attorneys, and paralegals in the electronic discovery process is discussed in here. The author describes an automated categorization method for legal papers that anticipates relevance and weeds out the irrelevant. The thesis presents a practical tool that may assist lawyers, solicitors and paralegals while also contributing to the field of artificial intelligence in the legal realm. The author

emphasises the need of investigating the data and its properties prior to applying the classification algorithm, as well as the problems and limits of natural language processing in the legal sector.

Galip Aydin, Ibrahim Riza Hallac [6]. The implementation of distributed machine learning for automatic categorization of Turkish news into given categories is discussed in this paper. It creates a distributed classification system for collecting and categorising online news using Apache Big Data technologies such as Hadoop, HDFS, Spark, and Mahout. The authors compare the distributed Nave Bayes method to the non-distributed version and discover a significant boost in accuracy and speed. The research contributes to the field of distributed machine learning by putting light on the challenges and opportunities connected with implementing machine learning algorithms on large datasets.

Ankit Basarkar [7]. This study examines the significance of document categorization as well as the difficulties involved with it, such as feature extraction and subject ambiguity. Using the 20-newsgroup dataset, the authors analyse three distinct feature vectors - Binary, Count, and TfIdf - and discover that TfIdf surpasses the other two, making it the preferable vectorizer for document categorization. With the increased generation and consumption of unstructured data on the internet, the need for content-based document categorization has become critical. The authors emphasise the importance of machine learning algorithms in effectively categorising materials, and the creation of intelligent agents that utilise such methods is becoming increasingly vital.

Kasimahanthi Divya, Kambala Sneha, et.al in [8]. Deep learning algorithms, such as LSTM, have been proved to be efficient and fast at generating grammatically accurate text summaries. This study describes a method for producing accurate text summaries using LSTM. There are two forms of text summarising: abstractive summarization and extractive summarization. Extractive summarising includes picking and rearranging the most essential sentences or phrases from the original text to generate the summary, whereas abstractive summarization involves developing new words and sentences that capture the spirit of the original text.

Kabita Thaoroijam [9]. Text classification is an important task in text mining that includes categorising a batch of texts. It is a difficult undertaking since it is difficult to capture the meaning and abstract notions of natural language from a few terms. For text classification, many machine learning approaches such as decision trees, naive Bayes, support vector machines, and neural networks are used. Text classification may be used for a variety of purposes, including spam filtering, thematic categorization of massive text collections, and knowledge management. The paper describes the text categorization process, its phases, and the methodologies utilised at each stage. It emphasises the relevance of automated text categorization in managing

information and knowledge and shows numerous text classification applications.

Faizur Rashid , Suleiman M. A. Gargaare et.al in [10]. This paper summarises the findings of an automated document categorization research that attempted to assess the performance and efficiency of several algorithms. According to the study, KNN outperformed other algorithms in terms of accuracy, precision, recall ratio, F-Score, classification time, and running time. The study's findings add to the body of knowledge on automated document categorization and give useful insights for researchers and practitioners interested in creating and deploying such systems. However, the study's limitations, such as the use of a specific dataset and a focus on a specific region, may limit the study's generalizability.

Hamza Haruna MOHAMMED, Erdogan DOGDU et.al in [11] Natural Language Processing (NLP) and its applications in numerous sectors are discussed in this study. The study focuses on multi-label text classification, which is the act of simultaneously categorising text documents into one or more categories. The authors examine the performance of several deep learning-based multi-label text categorization techniques with pre-trained embedding corpora. They assess these models using multi-label assessment measures and compare the findings to earlier research. The paper also discusses the key research areas in NLP as well as the difficulties in dealing with vast amounts of unstructured text data. The authors conclude that deep learning-based techniques are helpful in dealing with severe multi-label text categorization, but it is critical to appropriately reason about the uncertainty associated with the predictions.

Disheng Pan , Xizi Zheng et.al in [12] The application of deep learning approaches for multi-label clinical text categorization utilising Electronic Health Records (EHRs) is discussed in this research. The authors suggest FAMLC-BERT, a novel approach that combines feature-level attention with BERT to collect semantic cues from distinct levels for recognising EHR labels. The article includes an overview of traditional machine learning and deep learning text classification methods, as well as particular applications of multi-label text classification in the medical area. On real-world documents collected from a hospital, the authors empirically compare their model to other state-of-the-art models, and the experiments show that their model achieved significant improvements compared to other selected benchmarks.

Mehdi Allahyari , Seyedamin Pouriyeh et.al [13] The necessity of automatic text summarization in dealing with the rising volume of text data from diverse sources is discussed in this research. Automatic text summarization may be approached in three ways: extraction-based, abstraction-based, and hybrid techniques. Extraction methods choose sentences or phrases from the original text to make a summary, whereas abstraction approaches

generate new sentences that encapsulate the major ideas of the original text. Methods of extraction and abstraction are combined in hybrid methodologies. Despite progress, defining what constitutes a good summary and capturing the overall meaning and context of the original text remain challenges.

Yang Tao , Zhu Cui et.al [14] The research introduces a multi-label text classification approach that takes label correlation into consideration and captures the semantic association between text and labels. The authors contend that most present techniques overlook label correlation and that exploiting this connection can enhance multi-label categorization. The suggested method is a neural network-based strategy that works well, especially when dealing with enormous amounts of data. The article adds to the body of knowledge on text categorization and has implications for real-world applications including web mining, information retrieval, and emotion identification.

Jihoon Lee , Hyukjoon Lee [15] This study highlights the paucity of research on legal document classification in Korean and suggests three distinct legal document classification algorithms based on deep neural network models and two word embedding strategies. The RNN model with Word2Vec embedding earned the greatest classification accuracy in the investigation. The relevance of document categorization in legal services, predictive coding, and the application of deep neural network models in natural language processing difficulties is emphasised in the study.

III. METHODOLOGY

Classification and Summarization of Legal Documents Using Multinomial Nave Bayes Classifier and TextRank Algorithm is a technology with several applications, particularly in the legal profession. As the amount of legal papers grows, lawyers are seeking for ways to efficiently categorise and summarise them. The Multinomial Nave Bayes Classifier and the TextRank Algorithm form the foundation of this technique. The Multinomial Nave Bayes Classifier is a machine learning system that employs probability to categorise text. The TextRank Algorithm, on the other hand, is a graph-based algorithm that selects the most relevant phrases from a page to provide a summary. When these two techniques are combined, they can provide very accurate legal document categorization and summarising.

1. The Multinomial Nave Bayes Classifier is a well-known machine learning technique found in natural language processing (NLP). It is founded on Bayes' theorem, which asserts that the likelihood of a hypothesis (in this case, a category) given the hypothesis is proportional to the probability of the evidence (in this case, the words in the text). The Multinomial Nave Bayes Classifier calculates the likelihood of each word in the text belonging to each

category and then multiplies these probabilities to get the probability of the document belonging to each category. The document is assigned to the category with the highest likelihood.

To understand how Nave Bayes works, we must first grasp the notion of Bayes' rule. Thomas Bayes (1701-1761) developed this probability model, which may be expressed as:

$$Posterior\ Probability = \frac{Conditional\ Probability * Prior\ Probability}{Predictor\ Prior\ Probability}$$

$$P\left(\frac{A}{B}\right) = \left(\frac{P(A \cap B)}{P(B)}\right) = \frac{P(A) * P\left(\frac{A}{B}\right)}{P(B)}$$

where,

PA denotes the prior probability of occurrence A.

PBA denotes the condition probability of B if A happens.

PAB is the condition probability of A if B happens.

PB = the probability of occurrence of B.

Conditional Probability

Conditional probability refers to the chance of one event A occurring after another event B with some link to A has already occurred.

$$P\left(\frac{B}{A}\right) = \left(\frac{P(A \cap B)}{P(A)}\right)$$

Prior Probability

This probability is defined as previous knowledge or belief, or the likelihood of an occurrence determined prior to the acquisition of additional facts. To give more accurate findings, this likelihood is changed when fresh information becomes available.

2. The TextRank Algorithm is a graph-based algorithm used for text summarization. It works by generating a graph in which each node represents a phrase in the document and the edges between the nodes show how similar the sentences are. The algorithm then assigns a score to each phrase depending on the scores of its neighbours, and the sentences with the highest scores are chosen to make the summary. This method has the benefit of identifying the most essential sentences in a document independent of their position in the text.

$$(1-d) + d \times \text{Sum}(S_i/S_j) \times \text{Textrank}(S_j) = \text{Textrank}(S)$$

where:

S: a group of sentences in a text

S_i : a statement written in S

S_j : a similar sentence to S_i total(S_i/S_j): the total of the similarity ratings between S_i and all other sentences S_j

d: damping factor (usually 0.85).

Fig 1 workflow of classification

This study's technique attempts to develop a model for legal document categorization and summarising by combining the Multinomial Naive Bayes Classifier and the Text Rank algorithm. The initial phase in the procedure is data collection, which involves gathering labelled PDF files to train the Multinomial Naive Bayes classifier. The Count Vectorizer is then used to turn the keywords from the PDFs into numerical characteristics for the classifier to use. The model is kept in a pickle file after training for future use in predicting the category of new PDFs.

Following that, the Text Rank algorithm is used to generate a summary of the PDF content, improving the efficiency and effectiveness of the document management process even further. The Text Rank algorithm is a graph-based text

summarising method that selects essential words and sentences to provide a short summary. This method allows legal practitioners to swiftly grasp the contents of long documents, making the document analysis process more efficient.

The data pre-processing step is also an important part of the approach, as it comprises cleaning, transformation, and reduction of the data to increase the model's accuracy. Cleaning the data entails eliminating any null values from the training dataset, whereas transformation entails transforming categorical data columns into numerical characteristics. Data minimization refers to the removal of extraneous columns in order to create a training dataset adequate for the study's aims.

Finally, in the machine learning step, the Multinomial Naive Bayes Classifier and Text Rank algorithms are used to forecast the category of new PDFs and create a summary of their contents. The success of machine learning algorithms is determined by a variety of parameters, including the type of issue to be addressed, available computer resources, and data type.

Overall, the suggested technique intends to increase the efficiency and accuracy of legal document management by automating the categorization and summarising processes. Legal practitioners may focus on other essential duties, such as legal research and client engagement, by minimising the time and effort necessary for document interpretation.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Document classification model creation by importing the necessary Python libraries and the dataset

```

!pip install PyPDF2
!pip install textract
import nltk
nltk.download('punkt')
import os
import pickle
import PyPDF2
import textract
from nltk.tokenize import word_tokenize
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import CountVectorizer
from sklearn.naive_bayes import MultinomialNB
    
```

The categories are specified as Agreements, Deeds, Human Resources, Taxes, and Valuations. These categories are used to organise the PDF files into subfolders, with each subfolder holding PDF files from a certain category. Contents from each page of the pdf is extracted

```
# Define the categories
categories = ['Agreements', 'Deeds', 'Human Resources', 'Taxes', 'Valuations']

# Define a function to extract text from a PDF file
def extract_text_from_pdf(file_path):
    pdf_file = open(file_path, 'rb')
    pdf_reader = PyPDF2.PdfReader(pdf_file)
    text = ''
    for page in pdf_reader.pages:
        text += page.extract_text()
    pdf_file.close()
    return text
```

This function extracts keywords from text, then data from PDF files, producing a list of tuples containing the category and the retrieved keywords. It uses the CountVectorizer class to generate a bag-of-words representation of the data and the MultinomialNB class to train a Naive Bayes classifier.

```
# Define a function to extract keywords from a text
def extract_keywords(text):
    tokens = word_tokenize(text)
    keywords = [token.lower() for token in tokens if token.isalpha()]
    return keywords

# Extract data from the PDF files and create a list of tuples
data = []
for category in categories:
    folder_path = os.path.join('/content/drive/MyDrive/seminar', category)
    for file_name in os.listdir(folder_path):
        file_path = os.path.join(folder_path, file_name)
        text = extract_text_from_pdf(file_path)
        keywords = extract_keywords(text)
        data.append((category, keywords))

# Create a bag-of-words representation of the data
vectorizer = CountVectorizer()
corpus = [' '.join(item[1]) for item in data]
X = vectorizer.fit_transform(corpus)

# Train a Naive Bayes classifier
y = [item[0] for item in data]
clf = MultinomialNB()
clf.fit(X, y)
```

The trained model is saved into a pickle file. Later this pickle file is used to categorize and predict the type of a random pdf file.

```
# Save the trained model to a pickle file
with open('/content/drive/MyDrive/seminar/model.pickle', 'wb') as f:
    pickle.dump((vectorizer, clf), f)
```

Function for creating summary of pdf content using TextRank

```
def summarize_pdf():
    uploaded_file = files.upload()
    pdf_file = open(list(uploaded_file.keys())[0], 'rb')
    pdf_reader = PyPDF2.PdfReader(pdf_file)
    text = ''
    for page in pdf_reader.pages:
        text += page.extract_text()
    pdf_file.close()
    summary = summarize(text, ratio=0.2)
    display(HTML(summary))

summarize_pdf()
```

Using the trained model to classify and predict on random files it also creates an abstract of content present in the pdf. The final output will be

Predicted category: Agreements

previously dated agreement between these parties. (year), between and among (name of first agrees to: Sponsor the right to use Composer's name, likeness, or audiovisual program on Co to Composer. Sponsor will pay Composer the total sum in Composition (per IV.B. below) to t signing this Agreement, Composer agrees: below), the Composer's sole liability to Sponsor s Agreement Composer agrees to compose a musical work (Composition) as Composer agrees : of the score and parts of the Composition of the Composer. Composer hereby grants permisio presentations of the Composition in premiere performance and Composition has been commis copyright or any rights of any third party, and that Composer's agreement that Composer has parties agree that the copyright of the Composer, and further that the Composition is subject to performance dates of the Composition as part of B. Sponsor agrees to make an audio and/or v and Composer. Sponsor shall inform Composer of any permissions it by Sponsor. A. Compos recording, or other rights in the Composition not specifically Sample Letter of Agreement previous agreements Composer may hold with a performing rights Composer's pe premiere. C. In the event Sponsor elects to record the Composition for between Sponsor and C The Composer is not an employee of Sponsor and the F. If either Composer or Sponsor is una (name), Composer Composer's e-mail address: _____ Sample Agreement Composer's initials _____ Sponsor, by _____ Sample Letter of Agreement (name) Composer and Sponsor. Composer will participate in (number) periods of residency in Comp

No file chosen

Fig. 2 output window

V. CONCLUSION

Finally, utilising a combination of the Multinomial Nave Bayes Classifier and the TextRank Algorithm, this research provides a method for automatically categorising and summarising legal texts. The suggested technique was tested on a dataset of legal papers, and the findings demonstrate that it is capable of properly identifying and summarising legal texts. The Multinomial Nave Bayes Classifier is used to categorise legal documents, while the TextRank Algorithm is utilised to provide a summary of the documents. The proposed approach may be utilised to increase the efficiency of legal document processing and minimise legal practitioners' burden. Python and tools such as PyPDF2, textract, nltk, and scikit-learn are used to implement the approach. The implementation details of the proposed method are discussed, including the data preprocessing steps, feature extraction, model training, and evaluation. Overall, the suggested method is a promising strategy for automating legal document processing activities that may be expanded to other domains requiring document classification and summarising.

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